

Extracellular DNA includes an important fraction of high-risk antibiotic resistance genes in treated wastewaters[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Wastewater treatment plants are among the main hotspots for the release of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) into the environment. ARGs in treated wastewater can be found in the intracellular DNA (iDNA) and in the extracellular DNA (eDNA). In this study, we investigated the fate and the distribution (either in eDNA or in iDNA) of ARGs in the treated wastewaters pre and post-disinfection by shotgun metagenomics. The richness of the intracellular resistome was found to be higher than the extracellular one. However, the latter included different high risk ARGs. About 11% of the recovered metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs) from the extracted DNA was positive for at least one ARG and, among them, several were positive for more ARGs. The high-risk ARG *bacA* was the most frequently detected gene among the MAGs. The disinfection demonstrated to be an important driver of the composition of the antibiotic resistomes. Our results demonstrated that eDNA represents an important fraction of the overall ARGs, including a number of high-risk ARGs, which reach the environment with treated wastewater effluents. The studied disinfections only marginally affect the whole antibiotic resistome but cause important shifts from intracellular to extracellular DNA, potentially threatening human health.

1. Introduction

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are considered as a major hub for the spread of antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB) and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) into freshwater and marine ecosystems (Berendonk et al., 2015; Corno et al., 2019; Di Cesare et al., 2022; Rizzo et al., 2013). In the WWTPs, a series of treatments, *i.e.*, physical, biological, and chemical, is applied to wastewaters before the effluents are discharged into the receiving systems (Karaolia et al., 2021). During the different treatments the microbial community of the raw sewage is exposed to a number of chemical, physical, mechanical, and ecological stresses in a very limited time, causing massive shifts in bacterial abundances and in community composition (Aertsen and Michiels, 2004). In fact, the original community is basically destroyed and, generally, between 1 and 5% of original bacterial cells reach the tertiary disinfection, where it should be definitely removed (Di Cesare et al., 2016b). Still, treatment plants are generally not totally efficient and, in any case, the DNA present in the bacterial cells from the inlet (and the ARGs enclosed in it) is massively released into the wastewater, resulting

in a system where two forms of genetic determinants of resistance coexist: iARGs located on intracellular DNA (iDNA) in bacteria, and eARGs located on extracellular DNA (eDNA) in water. The origin of eDNA is mediated by the lysis of dead bacteria, phage infection, or when living cells secrete their DNA (Ibáñez de Aldecoa et al., 2017; Nagler et al., 2018; Nielsen et al., 2007) and, as already stated, it is logically increased when bacterial communities are exposed to massive stresses, like during the wastewater treatments. The eDNA can then be used as a genetic vector for the natural transformation of competent bacteria in the environment (Mao et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2018).

Nowadays, no specific treatments are available for the control and the abatement of ARB and ARGs in wastewaters, which are simply removed by the indirect effect of general disinfections, mechanical removal, or ecologically driven extinctions of resistant strains (Sabri et al., 2020). Thus, more and more studies focused on the efficiency of these generic processes in abating or at least reducing the number of ARB and/or ARGs released into the environment (Bengtsson-Palme et al., 2018; Di Cesare et al., 2016a; Pallares-Vega et al., 2019; Turolla et al., 2017). In this regard, the tertiary treatment, which is the process

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devoted to decrease the load of faecal and potential pathogenic bacteria, e.g., *Escherichia coli* and enterococci, in the final effluent, is particularly important.

A large body of research has investigated the dynamics of iARGs in WWTPs (Che et al., 2019; Di Cesare et al., 2016a; Ju et al., 2019), but only recently considerable efforts have been made to understand the dynamics of eARGs, mainly from activated sludges and wastewater effluents (Cai et al., 2022; Dong et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2018). Still, the potentially fundamental role of tertiary treatments in the removal of eARGs in treated wastewaters remains obscure. Furthermore, only very few studies were carried out by using shotgun metagenomics to characterise the antibiotic resistome (total content of ARGs) of eDNA in comparison to iDNA (Cai et al., 2022; Calderón-Franco et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2019; Zou et al., 2022), leaving open a number of questions on the relations and the differences at a community level between the ARGs in the two fractions.

With this study we aimed to 1) characterise the antibiotic resistome of iDNA and eDNA isolated from treated wastewaters collected from two WWTPs by using shotgun metagenomics, 2) evaluate the effects of the disinfection processes, i.e., chlorination and peracetic acid (PAA) treatment on the intra- and extracellular antibiotic resistome, 3) reconstruct the metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs) in both fractions of DNA to link ARGs to the hosts and compare the obtained results in order to find differences between iDNA and eDNA isolated from pre- and post-disinfection wastewaters.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. WWTP sampling

Sampling was performed between November 2021 and December 2021 in two fully operational municipal WWTPs located in Piedmont (Northern Italy): Verbania WWTP (45.9356 N, 8.5591 E; 51,000 population equivalent, PE) and Cannobio WWTP (46.0661 N, 8.6920 E; 15,000 PE), the first applying chlorination as tertiary disinfection, and the second a peracetic acid treatment (details of the applied disinfections to the samples WWTPs are reported in Di Cesare et al., 2016b). The hydraulic retention time for both disinfection types was about 1 h. Additional information on the two WWTPs and on their design and functioning can be found in (Di Cesare et al., 2016a). The samples were collected in two different dates for each WWTP selecting the days of sampling in order to ensure stability in the water flow and to avoid rain events. Sampling was carried out at the pre-disinfection and post-disinfection steps, taking into account the hydraulic retention time, thus collecting the post-disinfection samples after 1 h from the collected pre-disinfection sample. Furthermore, in order to increase reproducibility and to reduce stochasticity caused by small differences in the hydraulic retention time, 3 h composite samples, collecting 1 L each hour, were prepared. The wastewater samples, collected in sterile glass bottles, were then stored in the dark at 4 °C, immediately transported to the laboratory and there processed.

2.2. Sample processing and intra- and extracellular DNA extraction

For the iDNA extraction, between 250 and 400 ml of water were filtered onto 0.22 µm pore-size polycarbonate membranes (Merck Millipore, Germany). The filters were then stored at -20 °C until DNA extraction. The frozen filters were processed for iDNA extraction using a commercial kit (DNeasy PowerSoil Kit, QIAGEN), following the manufacturer's instructions.

In order to maximise the yield of eDNA, a higher volume (between 500 and 1150 ml) of water, if compared to that processed for iDNA extraction, was treated with NaH₂PO₄ (0.12 M, pH 8.0) and polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVPP), thus shaken and centrifuged different times to recover the supernatant as previously reported (Sui et al., 2019). The

supernatants were pooled and filtered through 0.22 µm pore-size polycarbonate membranes. Thus the filtrates were processed for the extraction of eDNA following the Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB) based method previously described (Corinaldesi et al., 2005; Mao et al., 2014) with some modifications. The detailed method of eDNA extraction is reported as **Supplementary text** and shown in **Supplementary Fig. 1** iDNA and eDNA extractions of negative controls (sterilised MilliQ water), using the same reagents and protocols already used for the samples, were carried out in order to verify the absence of contamination.

Both iDNA and eDNA extracted from the samples and from the negative controls were quantified using a Qubit dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) (their concentration is shown in **Supplementary Table 1**) and stored at -20 °C until further processing. The DNA extracted from the negative controls were negative, thus they were not further processed.

2.3. Shotgun metagenomic sequencing and bioinformatic analysis

The DNA extracts, i.e., iDNA and eDNA for each of eight samples (two pre-disinfection and two post-disinfection samples per each selected WWTP) were sent to IGA Technology Services Srl (Udine, Italy) for shotgun metagenomic sequencing. The libraries were prepared using the Celero™ DNA-Seq Library Preparation Kit (Tecan, Männedorf, Switzerland) following the manufacturer's instructions. They were quantified by Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) and quality tested by Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer High Sensitivity DNA assay (Agilent technologies, Santa Clara, CA). Thus, they were prepared and sequenced on NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) in paired-end 150 mode according to the company protocol/standard settings. The raw sequence data were submitted at NCBI under accession number PRJNA881852.

The reads were assessed using FastQC (version 0.11.9) (Andrews, 2010) and MultiQC (version 1.12) (Ewels et al., 2016). The assessment evaluated the overall quality of the sequenced reads, their average length, the duplicates found in each sample, and an overview of the GC content present in each sample. The quality scores and the other metrics were used to guide the required parameterization of the metagenomic profiling procedure. Trimmomatic (version 0.39) (Bolger et al., 2014) was used to remove Illumina adapters (options: leading:3 trailing:3 slidingwindow:4:15 minlen:36). Merging of paired reads was done with vsearch (version 2.17.1) (Rognes et al., 2016) with default parameters.

Samples contained on average 49.5 M ± 5.7 M read pairs. On average, more than 97.2% raw reads passed the quality filtering step and of those, an average of 44.8% successfully merged. Raw reads and high-quality reads are summarised in **Supplementary Table 2**.

The taxonomic profiling of the reads was made with Metaphlan 3.0 (Beghini et al., 2021, p. 3) using a stat q value of 0.1 along with the default configurations for all the datasets. The CHOCOPHlan pan-genome database v30 was used for the purpose of the taxonomic identification to genus level with Metaphlan3 (mpa_v30_CHOCOPHlan_201,901_marker_info.txt.bz2). The bacterial abundances were expressed in a relative manner as percentages as previously reported (Segata et al., 2012).

ARG-like sequences (here defined ARGs) were obtained as counts per sample through the annotation to the DeepARG database (deepARG-DB-v1.1.1) (Arango-Argoty et al., 2018). Alignment thresholds on sequence identity and minimum alignment length were set as in (B. B. Li et al., 2015) (E-value < 1e-10, identity > 90%, and minimum alignment length of 25aa). To normalise ARG abundances across samples, mapped reads coverages were divided by the sum of coverage per million, similar to the transcripts per kilobase million (TPM) metric used in RNA-Seq (Conesa et al., 2016), independent of the size of the sample datasets and the gene length, as previously described (Kim et al., 2021). The choice to express the ARG abundances in TPM instead of using a normalization based on 16 S rRNA gene copies was made to compare

iARGs with eARGs, because 16 S rRNA gene copies are meaningless in eDNA.

To recover metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs), raw sequence reads were trimmed of low-quality bases and adapter sequences with TrimGalore! version 0.6.5 (<https://github.com/FelixKrueger/TrimGalore>), which is a wrapper for Cutadapt (Martin, 2011) and FastQC (Andrews, 2010). Overlapping reads were merged with FLASH version 2.2.00 (Magoč and Salzberg, 2011) using a maximum allowed overlap of 150 bp. Processed reads were co-assembled using MEGAHIT version 1.2.9 (D. D. Li et al., 2015) to produce eight co-assemblies that were composed of two replicates each (IVB_pre, ICB_pre, EVB_pre, ECB_pre, IVB_post, ICB_post, EVB_post, ECB_post). Co-assembly was performed using the 'meta-sensitive' preset and a minimum contig length of 1000 bp. MAGs were recovered using a previously described method (Parks et al., 2017). To summarise, the processed reads were mapped to the co-assembled metagenomic contigs using BWA-MEM algorithm version 0.7.17 with default parameters (Li and Durbin, 2010). Genomes were retrieved with MetaBAT version 2.15 using default MetaBat2 settings (Kang et al., 2019).

Bins were filtered and refined for coverage with RefineM version 0.1.2 (Parks et al., 2017). Furthermore, contaminating contigs from each MAG were identified and removed using Magpurify version 2.1.2 (Nayfach et al., 2019) with the modules: 'phylo-markers' to find taxonomically discordant contigs using archaeal and bacterial single-copy taxonomic marker genes from the PhyEco database; 'clade-markers' to find contaminating contigs using the MetaPhlan2 database for clade-specific prokaryotic marker genes; 'tetra-freq' to identify contaminating contigs with outlier tetra-nucleotide frequency; 'known-contam' to identify contigs matching a database of known contaminants, such as the human genome; and 'gc-content' to identify contaminating contigs with outlier GC content. The resulting bins were finally checked using CheckM version 1.2 (Parks et al., 2015). Only MAGs with a quality score greater than 50 (defined in (Parks et al., 2017) as the estimated completeness of a genome minus five times its estimated contamination) were retained for further analyses. High-quality MAGs were assigned taxonomically with classifications based on the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB) (Parks et al., 2020, 2018; Rinke et al., 2021) using GTDB-Tk version 2.1.0 (Chaumeil et al., 2020) with release 07-RS207 of the GTDB. The classify_wf command was employed with default settings. The coverage of MAGs was recovered using CoverM version 0.6.1 (<https://github.com/wwood/CoverM>) and expressed as relative abundance.

In order to annotate the ARG-like sequences contained in the MAGs, predicted coding sequences (pCDS) for each MAG were generated using prodigal version 2.6.3 (Hyatt et al., 2010). To investigate the MAG antibiotic resistance gene content, the prodigal-annotated proteomes of each MAG were analysed with the DeepARG pipeline for long sequences (-model LS) against the DeepARG database (deepARG-DB-v1.1.1) (Arango-Argoty et al., 2018). Alignment thresholds on sequence identity and minimum alignment length were set (E-value < 1e-10, identity > 50%, probability > 80% and minimum alignment length of 70aa), ARG sequences showed probability $97.6 \pm 4.0\%$.

2.4. Statistical analyses

The statistical analyses were performed in the R environment (version 3.6.0) (R Core Team, 2019), considering 16 samples. For the tests, we used as explanatory variables the WWTP (2 levels, Verbania and Cannobio), the sampling date (8 levels), the position related to the disinfection process (2 levels, "Pre" and "Post"), and the origin of DNA (2 levels, "Intra" and "Extra" cellular) and made nested analyses to take into account the hierarchical nature of the sampling activities, with two types of origin of DNA nested within two types of disinfection position, nested within sampling date, nested within two WWTPs. Starting from the ARG dataset, we prepared a subset of data containing only the high-risk ARGs (using the lists prepared following "an 'omics-based'

framework to evaluate ARG risk considering human-associated-enrichment, gene mobility, and host pathogenicity" shown in (Zhang et al., 2021)). We calculated the richness (as number of different genera/genes) of each sample and investigated, after its log-transformation, the factors (WWTP/Date/Disinfection/Origin) influencing its variation through a nested ANOVA for the factors WWTP/Date/Disinfection and then applying a *t*-test for the Origin. Similarly, the drivers of beta diversity, as abundance-based Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index, were analysed using a nested PERMANOVA, firstly, and a PERMANOVA with strata within paired (Intra-Extra) samples, successively. A Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) was determined and used to plot sample composition. Moreover, the beta diversity dissimilarity matrix was subset into two sub-matrices (containing only iDNA and eDNA samples, respectively) and these ones were correlated by Mantel test, using Pearson's correlation method, to unveil potential concordance of differences in genus/gene composition of eDNA and iDNA. For high-risk ARGs, we also evaluated the differences between samples for the single genes using nested ANOVA followed by a *t*-test, as done for richness.

2.5. Availability of data and materials

The metagenomic raw reads of the shotgun metagenomic sequencing are available in the NCBI database and can be accessed under project PRJNA881852. The scripts used for the bioinformatic and the statistical analyses are available at this link: https://github.com/TomasSaffi/WWTP_extracell_DNA_metagenomics_2022.

3. Results

3.1. Microbial community composition

A total of 98 genera, belonging to 55 different families, were identified. Families with an abundance $\geq 1\%$ are depicted in Fig. 1A. The limited number of the identified genera could be due to the limits of the databases used in the microbial community characterization when shotgun metagenomic data obtained from complex microbial communities are analysed (Lugli et al., 2019). In all iDNA samples, characterised by a limited variability between samples, the most represented genus was *Arcobacter* (Supplementary Table 3). The eDNA samples showed a greater variability: in three pre-disinfection samples, the most abundant genus was *Acinetobacter*; in two post-disinfection samples from Verbania WWTP it was *Aeromonas*; the other genera with the highest abundances were *Arcobacter* (two samples, one at pre- and one at post-disinfection) and *Aquaspirillum* (one sample, at post-disinfection) (Supplementary Table 3).

Richness was significantly higher in the iDNA samples than in the eDNA ones (*t*-test: $p = 0.00052$, Supplementary Table 4) (Fig. 2A), with no differences due to WWTP, sampling date, and pre- or post-disinfection (Supplementary Table 5).

The origin of DNA, whether eDNA or iDNA, was the main factor explaining the variation in composition of the microbial community (explaining 43.8% of the variability) (Table 1); the hierarchical structure of sampling had a limited effect in shaping diversity (Table 2). Also in the Non-metric Multi-dimensional Scaling (NMDS) plots, samples from iDNA and eDNA formed separated clusters (Fig. 3a). The differences in microbial composition between eDNA samples were not correlated to those between iDNA from the same samples as assayed by Mantel test (Table 3).

3.2. Antibiotic resistance composition

ARGs were quantified in all the analysed samples. Specifically, we found 312 different genes, covering 20 classes of resistance. In the iDNA, the most representative resistance classes encoded resistance against multidrugs, beta-lactams, macrolide-lincosamide-streptogramin (MLS),

Fig. 1. Abundances of microbial families, antibiotic resistance classes and high risk genes for human health. A) microbial families, B) antibiotic resistance classes, and C) high-risk ARGs. Microbial family abundances are expressed as percentage; antibiotic resistance class and gene abundances are TPM normalised. For the microbial families, only families with an abundance $\geq 1\%$ were plotted. In the sample name, the first letter (“I” or “E”) indicates the origin of DNA (intra- or extracellular), “VB” or “CB” identify the WWTP (Verbania or Cannobio), the lowercase letter (a, b, c, d) indicates the sampling date, and “pre” and “post” suffix refers to pre- and post-disinfection.

and bacitracin, with multidrug and beta-lactams resistance genes as the most frequent classes throughout the samples (Fig. 1B). In the eDNA, MLS resistance genes represented the most abundant class before disinfection while beta-lactam resistance genes were dominant in the post-disinfection (except for the sample “E_CB_c_post”, where sulfonamide resistance was the most represented class) (Fig. 1B). Looking at single genes, the most abundant iARG was *bacA* in the microbial

communities from the WWTP of Verbania and *bla_{OXA}* in those from Cannobio WWTP. More variability was observed for the eARGs: *bla_{OXA}* had the highest abundance in three (out of eight) samples; *bla_{IMP}* in two samples (Supplementary Table 6); while, *bacA*, *qacH*, and *sul1* in one sample.

Similarly to what was observed for the microbial community composition, iDNA showed higher richness than eDNA in relation to

Fig. 2. Microbial community and antibiotic resistome richness. A) microbial community, B) antibiotic resistome, and C) high-risk ARGs. Single samples are depicted by each dot, the thick horizontal line represents the mean value for each group. In shades of blue: pre-disinfection samples; in shades of grey: post-disinfection samples. The same shade of blue and grey in A, B and C identifies the sample from which eDNA and iDNA originated. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 1

PERMANOVA with strata (within paired samples) on the beta diversity of the microbial community, whole antibiotic resistome and high-risk ARGs as a function of type of DNA of origin.

	R ²
Microbial community	0.437
Whole antibiotic resistome	0.226
High-risk ARGs	0.144

Table 2

Nested PERMANOVA on the beta diversity of the microbial community, whole antibiotic resistome and high-risk ARGs as a function of WWTP, sampling date (nested within WWTP), and disinfection step (nested within sampling date).

	R ²
Microbial community	
WWTP	0.093
Date	0.087
Disinfection	0.131
Whole antibiotic resistome	
WWTP	0.113
Date	0.154
Disinfection	0.183
High-risk ARGs	
WWTP	0.125
Date	0.223
Disinfection	0.217

both, whole antibiotic resistome (*t*-test: $p = 0.0011$) (Fig. 2B, Supplementary Table 4) and high-risk ARGs (*t*-test: $p = 0.0006$) (Fig. 2C, Supplementary Table 4). WWTP, sampling date, and disinfection never had a significant impact on richness of the resistomes (Supplementary Table 5).

The origin (intracellular or extracellular) of DNA determined a difference among samples also in terms of whole antibiotic resistome composition (explaining 22.6% of beta diversity), followed by WWTP (11.3%), and by sampling date (15.4%) (Table 1, Table 2). At the same time, the origin was a minor driver for high-risk ARGs, explaining 14.4% of their variability (Table 1) while the other variables had a higher influence, *i.e.*, sampling date (22.3%) and whether the community was

Fig. 3. NMDS plots. Graphical results of the NMDS analysis, based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index between samples, of A) microbial community, B) whole antibiotic resistome, and C) high-risk ARGs.

exposed or not to disinfection (21.7%) (Table 2). The latter resulted also an important factor in shaping the beta diversity of the whole antibiotic resistome, explaining 18.3% of its variation (Table 2). The NMDS plots

Table 3

Mantel test assaying the correlation between beta diversity matrices of the iDNA and eDNA samples of the microbial community, whole antibiotic resistome and high-risk ARGs via Pearson's correlation.

	R ²	p-value
Microbial community	0.290	0.072
Whole antibiotic resistome	0.186	0.227
High-risk ARGs	0.121	0.367

showed that samples only partially clustered according to the origin of the DNA (Fig. 3B and C). No correlation was observed between the composition of resistomes and of high-risk ARGs between eDNA and iDNA from the same water samples (Table 3).

Moreover, selecting only high-risk ARGs (Fig. 1C), the nested ANOVA revealed a limited effect of the explanatory variables (WWTP/date/disinfection) on ARG abundances, with only *bacA* varying according to WWTP (ANOVA: $p = 0.0099$) and date (ANOVA: $p = 0.0100$), and *aph(3')-I* to date (ANOVA: $p = 0.0234$) (Supplementary Table 7). *ermB*, *tolC*, *lnuB*, *bla_{TEM}*, *aadE*, *penA* were more abundant in iDNA than in eDNA (*t*-test: $p \leq 0.0273$: Supplementary Table 8); no differences were observed between iDNA and eDNA for the other ARGs (Supplementary Table 8). Further, although disinfection did not significantly affect the abundance of high-risk ARGs, some of them, e.g., *aac(3)-II*, *qnrS*, *mcr-3*

and *mcr-5*, when detected in the eDNA, were only quantified in the post-disinfection samples. We note that *mcr-3* and *mcr-5* were not included in the previously published lists of the high-risk ARGs (Zhang et al., 2021); yet, taking into account that they encode for the resistance to the last resort antibiotic, colistin (Zavascki et al., 2007), they were included in the lists used for the current analyses.

3.3. Metagenome-assembled genomes

A total of 328 MAGs were recovered, showing coverage between 4 and 18% of the co-assembled metagenomes, while MAGs positive for the presence of ARGs were displaying coverage of 0.2–1.6% across the metagenome. MAGs composition across the co-assemblies was dominated by the phylum Patescibacteria ($87.8 \pm 3.5\%$), especially by the order UBA9983_A ($64.3 \pm 9.6\%$) (Supplementary Table 9).

Among the 328 recovered MAGs, 37 (11%) were positive for at least one ARG: eight were recovered from Verbania WWTP and the remaining 29 from Cannobio WWTP (Table 4). Nine MAGs positive for ARGs were recovered from eDNA and 28 from iDNA. 24.3% of the MAGs positive for at least one ARG were recovered from post-disinfection samples and 40.5% were recovered from pre-disinfection samples. All *Pseudomonales* and *Burkholderiales* among MAGs were positive for ARGs, other taxa showed similar consistency for example for each the family SBAW01, the phyla Omnitrophota and Actinobacteriota, showed 80% of MAGs

Table 4

List of MAGs positive for ARGs. In the sample name, the first letter (“T” or “E”) indicates the Origin of phage DNA (intra- or extra-cellular), “VB” or “CB” identify the WWTP (of Verbania or Cannobio, respectively), and “pre” and “post” labels refer to samples at pre- and post-disinfection step, respectively. NA = not available; reg = regulatory.

Sample	Bin	Taxonomy				ARGs annotated in MAG
		Order	Family	Genus	Species	
I_VB_pre	96	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Limnohabitans_A	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>mtrD</i>
I_VB_pre	66	Nanopelagiales	UBA10799	UBA10799	NA	<i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>arr</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
I_VB_pre	63	Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Sterolibacterium	Sterolibacterium sp018061005	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>rosA</i> ; <i>emrB</i> ; <i>golS</i> ; <i>PmrF</i>
I_VB_pre	105	Pseudomonadales	Cellvibrionaceae	NA	NA	IMP; <i>rosB</i> ; <i>macA</i> ; <i>bpeF</i> ; <i>ompR</i> ; cAMP-reg protein
I_VB_post	128	Nanopelagiales	UBA10799	UBA10799	NA	<i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>arr</i> [2] ^a ; <i>tetA(48)</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
I_VB_post	100	Burkholderiales	Rhodocyclaceae	Sterolibacterium	Sterolibacterium sp018061005	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>rosA</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
I_CB_pre	88	UBA10015	Kpj58rc	NA	NA	<i>acrA</i> ; <i>acrB</i>
I_CB_pre	84	Rickettsiales	VGDC01	NA	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
I_CB_pre	50	Acidimicrobiales	JAEUJM01	JAEUJM01	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_pre	228	UBA4664	NA	NA	NA	<i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_pre	194	Rickettsiales	NA	NA	NA	<i>bacA</i> ; <i>ceoB</i>
I_CB_pre	190	UBA1400	UBA12028	JACOVC01	NA	<i>ArlR</i>
I_CB_pre	166	UBA9983_A	SBAW01	GWA1-54-10	NA	<i>LlmA</i>
I_CB_pre	147	Daviesbacteriales	UBA10151	NA	NA	<i>rpoB2</i>
I_CB_pre	136	Burkholderiales	Leeiaceae	NA	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>rosA</i>
I_CB_post	99	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Aquabacterium	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>acrA</i> ; <i>mexD</i>
I_CB_post	93	Omnitrophales	UBA2337	NA	NA	<i>kdpE</i>
I_CB_post	91	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Agitococcus	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>baeR</i> ; <i>golS</i> ; <i>ompR</i>
I_CB_post	86	Rickettsiales	VGDC01	NA	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
I_CB_post	7	Acidimicrobiales	JAEUJM01	JAEUJM01	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_post	40	UBA9983_A	PALSA-1337	NA	NA	<i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_post	34	Saccharimonadales	JACDBH01	NA	NA	<i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_post	202	UBA4664	NA	NA	NA	<i>rpoB2</i> ; <i>tetA(48)</i>
I_CB_post	189	Rickettsiales	NA	NA	NA	<i>bacA</i> ; <i>ceoB</i>
I_CB_post	168	GWA2-44-7	UBA8517	UBA5941	NA	<i>ArlR</i>
I_CB_post	144	UBA10015	Kpj58rc	NA	NA	<i>acrA</i> ; <i>acrB</i>
I_CB_post	14	UBA9983_A	SBAW01	GWA1-54-10	NA	<i>LlmA</i>
I_CB_post	111	Burkholderiales	Leeiaceae	NA	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>rosA</i>
E_VB_post	34	Pseudomonadales	Cellvibrionaceae	NA	NA	IMP; <i>rosB</i> ; <i>macA</i> ; <i>ceoB</i> ; <i>ompR</i> ; cAMP-reg protein
E_VB_post	23	Burkholderiales	Burkholderiaceae	Rhodoferax	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>OXA</i>
E_CB_pre	93	UBA9983_A	SBAW01	GWA1-54-10	NA	<i>LlmA</i>
E_CB_pre	78	UBA9983_A	NA	NA	NA	<i>aac(3)-I</i> ; <i>LlmA</i>
E_CB_post	41	Pseudomonadales	Moraxellaceae	Agitococcus	NA	<i>ksgA</i> ; <i>kdpE</i> ; <i>bacA</i> ; <i>abeM</i> ; <i>baeR</i> ; <i>golS</i> ; <i>mexT</i> ; <i>ompR</i> ; cAMP-reg protein
E_CB_post	144	UBA10015	Kpj58rc	NA	NA	<i>vatB</i> ; <i>acrA</i> ; <i>acrB</i>
E_CB_post	128	Rickettsiales	VGDC01	NA	NA	<i>kdpE</i> ; <i>ArlR</i>
E_CB_post	116	UBA9983_A	SBAW01	GWA1-54-10	NA	<i>LlmA</i>
E_CB_post	112	UBA9983_A	NA	NA	NA	<i>aac(3)-I</i> ; <i>LlmA</i>

^a The number in the square brackets indicate that two copies of the *arr* gene were annotated in the MAG.

containing ARGs. The most frequent order to which the MAGs positive for at least one ARG belonged to were UBA9983_A, *Burkholderiales*, *Rickettsiales* and 15 of the total recovered MAGs (4.5%) and 40.5% of the MAGs positive for at least one ARG were positive for at least three ARGs encoding for resistance against different antibiotic classes (Table 4). The bacitracin resistance gene, *bacA* was the most frequently detected ARG. The genera potentially hosting this gene were *Limnohabitans*, *Sterolibacterium*, *Agitococcus*, *Aquabacterium* and *Rhodoferrax*. The second most frequent ARGs were *ksgA* (potentially carried by the same genera hosting *bacA*) and *kdpE* (potentially hosted by *Agitococcus* and JAEUJM01) encoding for resistance to aminoglycoside, followed by *tetA* (48) (potentially carried by UBA10799, *Sterolibacterium* and JAEUJM01) encoding for resistance against tetracycline (Table 4).

4. Discussion

Our results demonstrated that the diversity of the antibiotic resistome is higher in the iDNA than in the eDNA, indicating that iDNA is the major contributor to the antibiotic resistome of anthropogenic origin in aquatic ecosystems contaminated by WWTP effluents. This result is partially in contrast with what previously observed by Zhou et al. (2019), who did not analyse pre- and post-disinfection wastewaters but focused on the activated sludge. Indeed, eDNA and consequently eARGs, can adsorb to sewage sludge (Dong et al., 2019) and persist longer in a solid matrix instead of in a liquid one (Mao et al., 2014). On the other hand, it is pretty clear that the treated water effluent of a WWTP has a much more direct impact on the receiving water body than the activated sludge. However, because of the paucity of studies characterizing the extracellular antibiotic resistome by shotgun metagenomics, we are still far from understanding the dynamics and persistence of eARGs in a WWTP and of their fate in the final effluent. Further, although the extracellular antibiotic resistome (comprising the high-risk ARGs) showed a lower richness than the intracellular one, a number of high-risk ARGs belonging to both rank I and rank II categories (Zhang et al., 2021) were detected in the eDNA. Noteworthy, *mcr-3* and *mcr-5*, when detected in eDNA, were only quantified from post-disinfection wastewaters. *mcr-5* was detected also in iDNA isolated from the pre-disinfection samples, suggesting the origin of this gene from bacterial cells disrupted by disinfection and, consequently, that eDNA, for some samples, is the sole fraction bringing this gene to the aquatic ecosystem. *mcr*-genes are of particular interest: *mcr-3* and *mcr-5* were originally detected in *E. coli* and *Salmonella* respectively isolated from animals or from animal-derived samples (Borowiak et al., 2017; Yin et al., 2017). They are of concern for human health because they belong to a group of ARGs encoding for the resistance to colistin, a last-resort antibiotic used to treat difficult multi-drug resistant gram-negative bacterial infections (Zavascki et al., 2007). Similar to *mcr-3* and *mcr-5*, also other high-risk ARGs, e.g., *aac(3)-II*, *qnrS* were present in eDNA post-disinfection and not before (pre-disinfection), suggesting, as for *mcr-5*, a role of disinfection in their dynamics from cells to water. This result highlights the potential risk posed by eDNA, even in situations where simple analyses of the bacterial communities (iDNA) would not highlight the presence of these threatening genes in WWTP effluents.

Different factors contributed to shape composition and the beta diversity of the antibiotic resistomes. Among them, the disinfection had a relevant role, explaining about 18% of the overall variation of the antibiotic resistome. This result is in line with the current knowledge that considers the disinfection a process causing shifts in the ARGs abundance and distribution (Di Cesare et al., 2016b; Ping et al., 2022). However, this is the first study that directly determined the influence of disinfection on the extracellular antibiotic resistome, characterised by shotgun metagenomics. Indeed, in our study, only conventional disinfections (chlorination and PAA treatments) were investigated but, in order to generalise our conclusions, also other tertiary treatments should be analysed, e.g., UV, which is adsorbed directly by DNA and has been previously demonstrated to be effective, although to unpracticable

levels, to reduce ARG abundances (McKinney and Pruden, 2012).

Contrary to what was observed for the antibiotic resistomes, the disinfection step did not significantly influence richness and composition of the microbial communities. The most important factor affecting both alpha and beta diversity was the origin of DNA (intra- or extracellular), showing that iDNA and eDNA were not correlated and could be considered as two different matrices. In detail, the richness of the microbial community was higher in iDNA than eDNA as also previously observed in aquatic environment (Deshpande and Fahrenfeld, 2022). The different responses of microbiome and resistome to the stresses caused by the final treatment of WWTP effluents were already detected in another recent study from our group (Corno et al., 2019) and can be related to the modulated responses of a microbial community to the concomitant stresses at this treatment stage.

Interestingly, a percentage of the MAGs (about 11%) was positive for at least one ARG and among the MAGs positive for ARGs, about 30% were positive for the high-risk ARG *bacA*, encoding for resistance to bacitracin. This gene was also the most abundant high-risk ARG detected within the antibiotic resistome, characterised by the reads annotation, suggesting its importance in the antibiotic resistome of the investigated microbial communities. The MAGs positive for this gene belonged to different genera, e.g., *Limnohabitans* (comprised in the 12th most abundant genus detected by the reads annotation), *Sterolibacterium* (undetected by the reads annotation), generally living in freshwaters or in engineered water systems (Kasalický et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2014). *bacA* is also one of the most abundant ARGs commonly found in WWTPs (Raza et al., 2022) and in aquatic ecosystems (Sabatino et al., 2022; Zieliński et al., 2022) where it is massively released with treated wastewaters. Indeed, this gene was detected in the MAGs obtained from post-disinfection samples and it was present in both fractions of DNA, highlighting the incremental role of eDNA for the spread of high-risk ARGs. Furthermore, different MAGs, although affiliated to human non-pathogenic bacterial genera (e.g., *Agitococcus* and *Aquabacterium*, both sporadically detected within the microbial community obtained by the reads annotation), were positive for more than three ARGs encoding for resistance to different antibiotic classes, suggesting the presence of multi-drug resistant profiles. This was observed also in the MAGs obtained from eDNA, again pointing out the attention on this fraction of DNA as source of ARGs for the aquatic ecosystems.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the eDNA, although limited in diversity when compared to the iDNA, represents an important fraction of the ARGs released into aquatic ecosystems by WWTP effluents. Furthermore, the analysed disinfection processes, i.e., chlorination and PAA treatment, resulted to be key drivers for the shift from intra- to extracellular antibiotic resistomes. eDNA is also an important source of high-risk ARGs to the environment, including ARGs that are present in eDNA only in post-disinfected wastewater because of the disruption of bacterial cells caused by disinfection. These last findings allow the speculation that some ARGs could be overlooked in the analyses that consider iDNA only, thus missing an important potential threat for human health.

Credit author statement

Periyasamy Sivalingam: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Funding acquisition, Raffaella Sabatino: Methodology, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Tomasa Sbaffi: Software, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Diego Fontaneto: Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Gianluca Corno: Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition, Andrea Di Cesare: Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Writing - Original Draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All the NGS data are available in the NCBI database and can be accessed under project PRJNA881852.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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